

BauXAItE: An Explainable AI Framework for UAV Multisensor-Driven Bauxite Stockpile Mapping and Classification

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Abstract—An explainable artificial intelligence (AI) framework for bauxite stockpile classification through uncrewed aerial vehicle (UAV)-driven mapping, BauXAItE, is introduced for efficient mineral resource assessment and monitoring. A UAV, equipped with RGB and multispectral sensors, is used to capture data within a broad spectrum range, allowing the analysis of the bauxite stockpiles spectral signatures. Two distinct datasets, RGB and multispectral, were created by utilizing photogrammetric tools to generate the orthophoto map and GIS for annotating the bauxite types. These datasets along with their combination, were used to train a pool of machine and deep learning models to classify spectral signatures into bauxite types. Experimental results demonstrated that, using a multilayer perceptron (MLP), the classification performance exceeded 91% across all standard metrics. To ensure model transparency, Kernel SHapley Additive exPlanations (SHAP) results accompanied the AI predictions, to indicate correlations between spectral bands and classification decisions, thereby supporting end-users toward practical deployment of bauxite resource management.

Index Terms—Bauxite, deep learning (DL), explainable AI (XAI) machine learning (ML), multispectral (MS), remote sensing (RS), SHapley Additive exPlanations (SHAP), uncrewed aerial vehicle (UAV).

I. INTRODUCTION

MATERIALS and minerals extracted from beneath the Earth's surface are critical for economic and social development due to them forming the foundation for industries ranging from construction and manufacturing to renewable energy and technology [1]. Streamlining and optimizing mining operations in an efficient and accurate way is therefore crucial in order to improve resource management, reduce waste, and ensure the

overall sustainability of the processes [2]. Recent technological advancements, particularly in the fields of remote sensing (RS), machine learning (ML), and deep learning (DL), have proven to be valuable tools in these optimizations, not only enhancing accuracy but also accelerating operations, significantly reducing costs, and improving efficiency [3].

Focusing on the technologies used, RS methods utilize satellites and uncrewed aerial vehicles (UAVs), usually equipped with RGB and/or multispectral (MS) sensors, to provide detailed information about the composition, distribution and extent of mineral deposits [4], [5], [6]. These methods rely on postprocessing techniques to extract meaningful insights for mineralogical and lithological applications, including data correction/calibration, image processing, dimensionality reduction, and RS indices calculation. Despite them being essential for basic surface analysis, they often fall short when handling more complex tasks, such as precision mineral analysis, soil classification, and detailed monitoring [4]. To address these limitations, research has shifted toward employing artificial intelligence (AI), as it has demonstrated effectiveness in handling multimodal data through its advanced predictive capabilities and capturing of underlying patterns, with ML algorithms recently gaining attention for mineral detection and mapping using MS data [7], [8], [9], [10], [11], [12].

Within the context of ML-based mineralogical and lithological mapping, there is a notable lack of focus on bauxite, the primary ore of aluminum, holding significant industrial importance. Although RS and satellite image processing techniques have been applied in this domain, much of the existing research does not focus on specific classification or identification of bauxite stockpiles [13], [14], [15], [16], [17], [18], [19]. Specifically, authors, such as [13] and [14], utilized Sentinel-2 images for mapping bauxite residues and active open mines, while the authors in [15] and [16] employed hyperspectral and copernicus data for spectral analysis and postprocessing in GIS tools. Advanced methods include the use of Gaussian models with HySpex and APEX images in [17] and ML techniques like support vector machines (SVM), Naïve Bayes, and random forest (RF) in [18] to study mining impacts. In addition, authors in [19] applied conditional Gaussian cosimulation with Sentinel-2 data to map metal concentrations in bauxite residues.

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Overall, while AI, satellite images and RS combination are being used extensively in mineral exploration, their application to bauxite identification remains underdeveloped [4], [7], [20], [21]. Many works in bauxite stockpile classification and identification rely on conventional processing techniques that involve the process of collecting ground samples and performing spectroscopy lab analysis on them [22], [23]. Deviating from the latter, other methodologies are largely confined to the use of satellites [13], [14], [15], [16], [17], [18], [19], which despite being rich in spectrum information they face several limitations: 1) their orbit-dependent data acquisition can result in incomplete spatial coverage of specific areas of interest, requiring additional processing steps, such as mosaicking or temporal compositing, when a location is not fully captured within a single tile [24], [25]; 2) their high spatial resolution and tiling scheme are optimized for large-scale monitoring, which may reduce effectiveness for detailed, localized analysis [26]; and 3) they typically demand extensive preprocessing, including atmospheric and radiometric correction, as well as cloud and shadow removal [27], [28]. On the other hand, UAVs support on-demand user-defined region mapping with high ground sampling distance and operate below cloud level, making them particularly valuable for monitoring dynamic and continuously evolving environments. Motivated by the above, this work introduces BauXAItE, an end-to-end framework that couples AI and explainable AI (XAI) to map and classify bauxite stockpiles, supporting localized mineral resource management and monitoring through UAVs. Specifically, the contributions of the proposed work are as follows.

- 1) Targeted area mapping and on-demand data acquisition of bauxite stockpiles using UAVs.
- 2) Data collection from RGB and MS sensors covering a broad spectrum range.
- 3) In-depth postprocessing procedure for geospatial notation and analysis.
- 4) Use of ML and DL models applied on RGB, MS data and their combination to effectively map bauxite stockpiles with improved performance.
- 5) Incorporation of Kernel SHapley Additive exPlanations (SHAP) for model-agnostic interpretations to assist end-users with the AI predictions.

The rest of this article is organized as follows. Section II introduces the proposed BauXAItE framework and analyzes in detail each of its processing steps. Section III cites the classification performance for all AI models used, both ML and DL, for three distinct datasets, namely, RGB, MS, and RGB and MS combination, while Section IV presents Kernel SHAP XAI summary plots for each one of the classes considered and provides analysis of the results. Section V offers a broader interpretation of the SHAP XAI findings, discusses upon them and further supports the use of Kernel SHAP and its feature importance attribution through band-specific exclusion use-cases. Finally, Section VI concludes this article and offers insights regarding future directions.

II. PROPOSED BAUXAITE FRAMEWORK

The workflow of the proposed BauXAItE framework is demonstrated in Fig. 1, while an in-depth analysis of each processing step included, is explained in the following sections.

A. Dataset Collection

The dataset collection was conducted in Agios Nikolaos, located in Boeotia, Central Greece. It is an industrial area, as shown in Fig. 2, containing bauxite stockpiles originating from Europe, Africa, and South America, with each bauxite stockpile coming with its own mineralogical composition. For data acquisition, a DJI Mavic 3 M was utilized, a compact and portable UAV equipped with an RGB and a MS camera sensor. The RGB sensor captures visible light in three bands corresponding (approximately) to wavelengths blue (450–495 nm), green (495–570 nm), and red (620–750 nm), whereas the MS sensor captures wavelengths in four specific bands corresponding to wavelengths Green (MS-Green) $560 \text{ nm} \pm 16 \text{ nm}$, Red (MS-Red) $650 \text{ nm} \pm 16 \text{ nm}$, RedEdge (MS-RedEdge) $730 \text{ nm} \pm 16 \text{ nm}$, and near-infrared (MS-NIR) $840 \text{ nm} \pm 26 \text{ nm}$.

The UAV operated at an altitude of 110 m, covering an area of approximately 88826.3 m^2 . Note that the reason for selecting this altitude is due to environmental limitations, where a flight below 110 m would result in collision with high-voltage power stations existing within the area. Therefore, 110 m is the minimum allowable altitude resulting in highest ground sampling distance. Preflight settings included a ground sampling distance of 5.08 cm/pixel and an image overlap of 80% for accurate reconstruction. The overlap value was selected to ensure comprehensive coverage of the area, particularly given the complexity of the industrial landscape and the relatively high flight altitude. Specifically, a high degree of overlap improves the spatial resolution and continuity of the orthomosaic and digital elevation model, particularly in areas with dense structural features or varied elevation [29]. Moreover, structure from motion (SfM) and multiview stereo (MvS) photogrammetric techniques, which are used in our postprocessing workflow, rely on the availability of multiple overlapping images taken from varying perspectives to generate accurate 3-D reconstructions and high-fidelity orthophotos. This overlap also helps minimize potential data voids caused by occlusions or reflective surfaces and improves tie point matching and geometric accuracy in the resulting models.

The drone covered a flight path of 2.63 km, capturing a total of 690 overlapping images, distributed as 138 images per spectral modality. The resulting dataset consists of two distinct formats: high-resolution RGB images with 5280×3956 pixels in JPEG format, and MS images for all bands in 16-bit GeoTIFF format with 2592×1944 pixel resolution. Note that during drone flight, the number of available stockpiles was 12 in total, a number corresponding to the total number of classes.

Fig. 1. Overview of the proposed BauXAItE framework. A UAV equipped with RGB and MS sensors is used for field data collection. For generating RGB and MS orthophoto maps, SfM and MVS algorithms are used along with a GIS tool. For geospatial annotation, metallurgy and mining engineering experts provide domain-specific knowledge that is used for polygon delineation and finally random points selection within them for dataset creation. ML and DL models are applied to the data for bauxite categorization and mapping, while Kernel SHAP XAI couples them to effectively interpret the model predictions.

Fig. 2. Industrial area containing different bauxite stockpiles in Boeotia, Central Greece. Image taken from Google Maps.

B. Data Postprocessing

Once the data acquisition is completed, an essential post-processing stage is required, that is the generation of the orthophoto map. In detail, the images captured by the DJI Mavic 3 M are fed to WebODM, an open-source API integrating two advanced photogrammetrical tools based on image processing techniques, 1) open structure from motion (OpenSfM) and 2) open multiview stereo (OpenMVS). OpenSfM forms the backbone of the reconstruction pipeline, determining camera orientation and generating a sparse 3-D point cloud through robust feature detection and matching. Building on this, OpenMVS processes the sparse cloud and camera orientation to produce

a dense, textured 3-D model, completing the photogrammetry workflow.

The generated orthophoto maps are integrated into QGIS software to create geospatial annotations in vector format. This is achieved by drawing small-scale polygons directly onto the orthophoto, allowing precise georeferenced mapping of the bauxite types identified in the image. It should be noted that the polygon boundaries are determined through a combination of in-situ inspection and orthophoto interpretation by a metallurgy expert. After the annotation, QGIS's random points in polygon is used, a tool for generating random points directly within the annotated bounding boxes representing the bauxite stockpiles based on uniform random sampling. The total number of points selected here is equal to 20 000, with their distribution shown in Fig. 3. To verify the dataset's balance, the Shannon Equitability index is used [30], measured as the ratio of the Shannon entropy to the maximum diversity, formally defined as

$$E = \frac{H}{\log_2(C)} \quad (1)$$

where $H = -\sum_{c=1}^C p_c \log(p_c)$ is the Shannon entropy, p_c is the frequency of each class and C corresponds to the number of classes equal to 12. Using (1) along with the number of points per class (see Fig. 3), the resulting value $E = 0.97$, a value almost 1, demonstrates the dataset's balance. The final step of the post-processing stage involves a two-way intersection process to prepare the dataset for ML processing. The first one, links each point to the annotated polygons, assigning the corresponding bauxite type and ensuring accurate categorization. The second one extracts spectral information by linking points to both the orthophoto's RGB image layer and the MS image layer, capturing reflectance values for spectral analysis. An illustration of the above post-process steps are shown in Fig. 4.

Fig. 3. Dataset class distribution. Total number of points is equal to 20 000.

C. Intelligent Processing

At this stage, popular supervised ML and DL models are used for classifying bauxite stockpiles. Specifically, BauXAIte framework incorporates ML algorithms, such as decision tree (DT), random forest (RF), XGBoost, LightGBM (LGBM), multi-class support vector machine (SVM) and multi-layer perceptron (MLP), while to account for DL models, a tabular convolutional neural network (TabCNN) is employed. To fully explore the ML algorithms potentials, hyperparameter optimization is applied to investigate, which ones result in the highest classification performance. Specifically, the hyperparameters considered for each ML model include 1) DT: max depth and features, min samples split and leaf, criterion; 2) RF: number of estimators, max depth and features, min samples split and leaf; 3) XGBoost: number of estimators, max depth, learning rate, subsample, colsample bytree, min child weight and gamma; 4) LGBM: same parameters as in XGBoost along with number of leaves, reg alpha and lambda; 5) SVM: C, gamma, kernel, decision function shape; and 6) MLP: hidden layer size, activation function, solver, alpha, learning rate, max iterations and batch size. The hyperparameter tuning was conducted using RandomSearchCV from scikit-learn [31], parameterized with 20 iterations and three-fold cross-validation ($cv=3$), resulting in a total of 60 model fits per ML model. Regarding TabCNN's architecture, its first processing block is composed of 1-D convolution layer with 32 filters of kernel size 3 followed by batch normalization and ReLU activation function. This is succeeded by a second processing block, identical to the first one, but with 64 filters. For effectively aggregating the learned feature maps, adaptive max pooling is applied, while a dropout equal to 0.2 was used to mitigate potential overfitting. As its final layer, a fully connected one is used. Considering TabCNN's training parameters, the batch size was set to 32, while the learning rate was set to 10^{-4} with an Adam optimizer.

For all ML and DL models, the data was initially split into 80% for training and 20% for testing, while computational

performance was evaluated using standard classification metrics including accuracy, precision, recall and F1-score. Moreover, min-max normalization is applied to the data reflectance values. To better understand the reasoning of the model decisions the XAI technique Kernel SHAP is used. Its purpose is to introduce positive and negative correlations to each feature, in our case bands, given input points corresponding to bauxite stockpile types. Formally, for a number of features $m = 1, \dots, M$, a dataset $D = \{(x_n, y_n) \mid n = 1, \dots, N\}$, and a predictive non-linear model $\hat{y}_n = f(x_n)$ approximating y_n , Kernel SHAP's goal is to compute the Shapley values ϕ_m representing the contribution of each feature m to the model's prediction. To achieve this, Kernel SHAP utilizes simplified binary representations $z_n \in \{0, 1\}^M$ and approximates a linear relationship as

$$g(z_n) = \phi_0 + \sum_{m=1}^M \phi_m z_{n,m} \quad (2)$$

where ϕ_0 is the initial feature attribution value. Considering that there exist a subset of inputs not contributing equally important to the model's prediction, Kernel SHAP utilizes weights to scale their importance as

$$\pi_{x'_n}(z_n) = \frac{(M-1)}{\binom{M}{|z_n|} |z_n| (M - |z_n|)} \quad (3)$$

where $x'_n \in \{0, 1\}^M$ are interpretable inputs converted through a mapping function $x_n = h_x(x'_n)$, defined as $h_x: \{0, 1\}^M \rightarrow \mathcal{X} \subseteq \mathbb{R}^M$ indicating if a feature is included ($x'_n = 1$) or excluded ($x'_n = 0$). Finally, using (2) and (3) the best estimates for ϕ_m are calculated by minimizing the following loss function as:

$$\mathcal{L}(f, g, \pi_{x'_n}) = \sum_{z \in Z} \pi_{x'_n}(z) (f(h_x(z)) - g(z))^2 \quad (4)$$

where $z \in \{0, 1\}^M$ is any binary mask vector (independent of the sample) and $Z \subseteq \{0, 1\}^M$ is the set of all sampled binary vectors.

The classification performance of the ML and DL models using RGB, MS, and RGB and MS data combination are cited in Table I. For each one of the datasets the results are discussed below.

RGB data: Among the ML and DL models evaluated, RF achieves the highest accuracy, recall, and F1-score, while TabCNN results in the highest precision value. In terms of accuracy, TabCNN closely follows RF with 75.50%, while DT exhibits the lowest among them with value equal to 66.65%. A similar trend is observed across the precision, recall, and F1-score metrics, but with TabCNN leading the precision values. Notably, the classification performance of the MLP falls short of RF, despite its ability to capture complex patterns in high-dimensional data.

MS data: For the MS data case, it can be seen that TabCNN achieves the highest accuracy, precision, recall, and F1-score, having also the highest overall performance compared to the rest models considered. The second-best performance is exhibited by RF with values close to those of the TabCNN, while the MLP falls behind RF, XGBoost, LGBM, and TabCNN. Compared to the evaluation using RGB only, it can be seen that when using

Fig. 4. Geospatial annotation creation procedure. Orthophoto: The orthophoto map is loaded to QGIS. Polygon annotation: A metallurgy expert performs in-situ inspection and orthophoto interpretation of the area for bauxite stockpile boundary box identification. Random points generation: QGIS random points in polygon generated uniformly distributed random points within the polygons. Pixel-value sampling: A two-way intersection process prepares the dataset; the first links each sampled point to the bauxite stockpile type while the second extracts spectral information by linking points to the RGB-MS layers.

TABLE I
CLASSIFICATION METRICS FOR ML AND DL MODELS ACROSS MULTIPLE DATASETS

Algorithm	RGB				MS				RGB + MS			
	Accuracy	Precision	Recall	F1 Score	Accuracy	Precision	Recall	F1 Score	Accuracy	Precision	Recall	F1 Score
DT	66.65	66.73	66.65	66.56	74.10	74.13	74.10	74.06	78.70	78.81	78.70	78.72
RF	75.52	75.61	75.52	75.40	80.13	80.11	80.13	80.05	87.65	87.74	87.65	87.66
XGBoost	75.42	75.56	75.42	75.29	79.17	79.16	79.17	79.07	88.75	88.88	88.75	88.78
LGBM	75.30	75.39	75.30	75.17	78.95	78.96	78.95	78.85	88.90	89.02	88.90	88.92
SVM (multiclass)	71.75	72.04	71.75	71.42	74.10	75.88	74.10	73.15	85.50	85.93	85.50	85.56
MLP	74.90	74.82	74.90	74.69	76.82	78.69	76.82	76.36	91.13	91.19	91.13	91.13
TabCNN	75.50	76.11	75.50	75.24	80.60	80.74	80.61	80.43	89.37	89.15	89.36	89.34

Bold font highlights the highest performance across all metrics among the compared models.

MS data in the TabCNN case the metric values have increased up to approximately 5.1%, in the RF case the metric values have increased up to approximately 5%, while DT ones have an increase of almost 8%. For the XGBoost, LGBM, SVM, and MLP there is an increase in the metrics values ranging from 2% to 4%.

RGB and MS data combination: With the RGB and MS data combination, it can be observed that among the ML algorithms, MLP achieves the highest classification performance with values surpassing 91% in all metrics considered. TabCNN comes second in performance with values up to 2% less than those of the MLP and approximately 1% higher than those of the LGBM, which results in the third highest performance values. Of important interest is the performance of the RF, which despite resulting in the best one when using RGB and satisfactory when using MS data only, in the RGB and MS data combination case it achieves more than 87% in accuracy, precision, recall and F1-Score, showing reduced relative performance compared to the rest models. It should be noted that the combination of RGB and MS data along with the MLP results in improved classification performance accuracy-wise compared to using only RGB or MS data along with the RF algorithm, corresponding to an increase in performance by more than 15%, compared to RGB and RF, and by more than 10%, compared to MS and RF. The hyperparameters values for all models yielding the results cited in Table I are listed in detail in Table II.

The results from Table I demonstrate the effectiveness of the MLP in capturing complex patterns of high-dimensional data

which is when the number of features, i.e. bands, increases to 7 while when the number of features is smaller, either three (RGB) or four (MS), other models perform better. In addition, of particular interest is TabCNN's performance compared to that of the MLP when RGB and MS data are used. While one may expect that the convolution operation from TabCNN will capture better the local spatial features correlations, this is in fact not the case as feature ordering in tabular data does not exhibit local characteristics [32], [33]. This makes the MLP a better-suited model given that it does not follow spatial or sequential structure in its processing, treating the features independently.

Apart from the average classification performance, it is reasonable to further investigate the performance for each individual class. To this end we select the RGB and MS data combination case and the highest performing model, namely, the MLP and provide the results in Table III, while its corresponding confusion matrix of actual and predicted classes is shown in Fig. 5. Focusing on the precision metric, the Europe-D bauxite stockpile resulted in the lowest performance, while, the MLP achieved the highest precision score on the Europe-B class with value 99.99% suggesting that nearly all instances classified were correct. In terms of recall, the MLP performed best for the Europe-B class, indicating that it successfully identified all actual instances without any omissions. Similarly to the precision, the Europe-D class resulted in the lowest performance. Regarding the F1-score, the Europe-B class excelled with value 99.88%, following its scores in precision and recall, while the Europe-D

TABLE II
HYPERPARAMETER VALUES FOR MODELS TRAINED AND TESTED ON
COMBINED RGB AND MS DATA

Model	Hyperparameters
DT	min samples split: 2 min samples leaf: 1 max features: SQRT max depth: 40 criterion: gini
RF	number of estimators: 200 min samples split: 2 min samples leaf: 1 max features: SQRT max depth: 30
XGBoost	subsample: 0.6 number of estimators: 200 min child weight: 1 max depth: 10 learning rate: 0.1 gamma: 0.1 colsample bytree: 0.8
LGBM	subsample: 1 lambda: 0.5 alpha: 0.1 number leaves: 50 number of estimators: 300 min child samples: 20 max depth: 6 learning rate: 0.1 colsample bytree: 0.8
SVM (multiclass)	kernel: poly gamma: 1 decision function: one-versus-rest C: 100
MLP	optimization: SGD max iterations: 300 learning rate: adaptive (initial 0.1) hidden layer: (300, 100) batch: 64 regularization alpha: 10^{-3} activation: ReLU
TabCNN	batch: 32 epochs: 200 optimizer: Adam loss: Cross Entropy learning rate: 10^{-4}

TABLE III
MLP CLASSIFICATION METRIC RESULTS FOR EACH CLASS

Bauxite Class	Precision (%)	Recall (%)	F1-Score (%)
Africa-A	89.47	94.97	92.14
Africa-B	90.43	87.63	89.01
Europe-A	87.56	91.50	89.49
Europe-B	99.99	99.75	99.88
Europe-C	88.69	93.78	91.16
Europe-D	80.46	82.98	81.70
Europe-E	93.69	90.19	91.90
Europe-F	93.51	96.77	95.11
South America-A	98.73	97.74	98.23
South America-B	94.26	90.02	92.09
South America-C	86.13	85.71	85.92
South America-D	89.11	86.57	87.82

class resulted in the lowest performance as anticipated due to the harmonic mean nature of the F1-score metric. This performance drop from Europe-D class is potentially attributed to similar physical and/or spectral characteristics to those existing in other classes from other region, namely South America C and D, as highlighted in Fig. 5.

Fig. 5. Confusion matrix corresponding to the classification using MLP. The dataset used is RGB+MS.

To further showcase the applicability of the proposed framework, Fig. 6 presents visualization results for a targeted area existing within the one shown in Fig. 2. The left part of Fig. 6, shows the original RGB image providing a visual reference for the scene, while the middle part displays the MS composite (NIR–Red–Green), which enhances spectral differences not visible in RGB. The right part depicts the inference results depicted in a map, where the MLP model effectively distinguishes between the different classes corresponding to bauxite stockpiles existing within the area. Small areas of mixed bauxite types can be observed between stockpiles, potentially attributed to vehicle operations in which material is loaded, transported, and redistributed between stockpiles. This mixing is most evident along the corridor leading to the stockpiles, where mineral transfer is most frequent.

IV. BAUXAITE FRAMEWORK: KERNEL SHAP INTERPRETATIONS BY GEOGRAPHIC REGION

In this section, we use the MLP model and the RGB and MS dataset combination to calculate the Kernel SHAP results. Then, to interpret the predictions we visualize the results in Fig. 7 for Africa and South America and in Fig. 8 for Europe. These visualizations illustrate the relative importance and impact of each spectral feature across both RGB and MS sensors on the MLP’s decision for specific bauxite classes. Each dot represents a single input sample, with color indicating the reflectance value and horizontal position reflecting the magnitude and direction of the feature’s contribution to the classification output.

A. South America Bauxites

In Fig. 7, the SHAP summary plot for the South America-A class reveals that RGB-Red, RGB-Blue, and MS-NIR are the most influential bands contributing to the model’s predictions. Notably, RGB-Red demonstrates a strong negative impact on the model output when its values are high, suggesting that

Fig. 6. MLP classification results of targeted area with bauxite stockpiles. Left: RGB image. Middle: MS false-color composite (NIR-Red-Green). Right: MLP inference results for the classified bauxite stockpiles using combined RGB and MS data.

Fig. 7. Kernel SHAP summary plots for South America classes A–D (top–first column bottom) and Africa classes A–B (second and third column bottom).

Fig. 8. Kernel SHAP summary plots for Europe classes A–F.

increased reflectance in this band decreases the likelihood of a pixel being classified as South America-A. In contrast, the South America-B bauxite class highlights RGB-Green as the most impactful feature in the model’s decision-making process. High reflectance values are associated with strong positive SHAP values, indicating that increased reflectance levels in the green channel significantly contributes to classifying samples

as South America-B. Conversely, low reflectance values in this band negatively influence the prediction. The RGB-Blue and MS-Green bands also show considerable importance, further supporting the role of shorter wavelengths in distinguishing this class.

For the South America-C class, the SHAP summary plot displays a more balanced distribution of feature contributions

across several spectral bands, with MS-NIR, MS-Green, and RGB-Blue being the most influential. The MS-NIR band exhibits the widest SHAP value spread, particularly with low reflectance values contributing negatively to the prediction, while mid-to-high values slightly support class identification. Meanwhile, the MS-Green and RGB-Blue bands demonstrate positive contributions, especially at higher reflectance levels. This suggests that greener and bluer pixel intensities are favorable indicators for detecting South America-C stockpiles. Finally, the SHAP summary plot for the South America-D class illustrates a more diverse contribution of spectral bands, with RGB-Green, RGB-Red, and MS-Green having the most influential roles. Among them, RGB-Green is particularly important with high reflectance values strongly pushing the prediction towards this class (positive SHAP values), while lower values having a negative impact. This underscores the importance of the green visual band in identifying the spectral signature of South America-D bauxites. Similarly, both RGB-Red and MS-Green contribute meaningfully to the model's decision, with high values associated with increased classification confidence.

B. African Bauxite Classes

Having analyzed the spectral contributions for the South American bauxite stockpiles, we now focus on African classes in Fig. 7. The SHAP summary plot for the Africa-A bauxite class MS-NIR, MS-Red, and MS-RedEdge show slightly higher influence compared to others. MS-NIR exhibits mostly negative SHAP values, especially for low reflectance values, which suggests that lower NIR responses reduce the probability of a pixel being classified as Africa-A. MS-Red and MS-RedEdge demonstrate a mixed influence across varying reflectance values. Their contributions are centered closer to zero (x -axis) but still show small shifts toward both negative and positive directions, hinting at their supportive role in shaping the decision boundary. In the case of the Africa-B bauxite class, the most influential features differ slightly, with MS-NIR, RGB-Green, and MS-Green emerging as the most important contributors to the model's predictions. MS-NIR stands out slightly with mostly negative SHAP values when reflectance is low, suggesting that low NIR responses reduce the likelihood of classifying a sample as Africa-B. RGB-Green and MS-Green both exhibit symmetric SHAP value spreads around zero, with high reflectance values occasionally influencing the prediction positively. This suggests that greener tones in both the visible and MS domains slightly favor classification into this bauxite type.

C. European Bauxite Classes

Fig. 8 presents the SHAP summary plots for the European bauxite stockpiles identified within area. Specifically, for the Europe-A class the SHAP summary plot indicates that the most relevant features are RGB-Red, MS-RedEdge, and RGB-Green. RGB-Red demonstrates the strongest SHAP value spread, with higher reflectance values contributing positively to the class prediction. This suggests an association between red reflectance and the Europe-A bauxite spectral signature. MS-RedEdge and

RGB-Green follow closely in importance. While their contributions remain close to zero on average, there are instances where certain reflectance levels contribute either positively or negatively, implying a context-dependent influence on classification. Similar to Europe-A, Europe-B class shows a well-defined feature importance pattern, with RGB-Blue, RGB-Red, and RGB-Green influencing the model's decisions. RGB-Blue is the most critical feature, where low reflectance values have strong negative SHAP values, reducing the model's confidence in classifying a pixel as Europe-B. In contrast, high reflectance increases the likelihood of this class being predicted. This suggests that bright blue tones are a strong positive indicator for Europe-B. RGB-Red and RGB-Green also show significant positive influence when reflectance is high, contributing to a clearer RGB-based spectral identity.

In the case of Europe-C class SHAP values reveal a balanced distribution of feature contributions across all spectral bands. The model's decision is influenced by many bands modestly, without a single dominant feature. The RGB bands, especially RGB-Blue and RGB-Red, show the most consistent, though still limited, positive influence when reflectance values are high. This suggests that brighter pixels in the visible spectrum slightly increase the likelihood of classification into Europe-C. The MS bands present small SHAP variations around zero. Their influence is minimal, with a few high-reflectance points pushing the prediction positively. A more dynamic contribution pattern appears in the Europe-D class, where both RGB and MS features are present. The MLP's predictions for this class are primarily influenced by RGB-Blue, RGB-Green, and RGB-Red, followed by MS-NIR and MS-Green. RGB-Blue stands out as the most impactful feature, where low reflectance values strongly decrease the probability of predicting Europe-D (negative SHAP values), while higher reflectance values contribute positively. This reveals a distinct blue signature that guides the model's confidence for this class. RGB-Green and RGB-Red also provide meaningful input to the classification. High reflectance in both bands moderately increases the likelihood of predicting Europe-D, but their impact is less extreme than RGB-Blue.

In contrast to the previously mentioned classes, the Europe-E class highlights a strong influence from MS-NIR, MS-Red, and MS-Green, making this class one of the most important on MS data so far. MS-NIR stands out as the most impactful feature, where low reflectance values contribute significantly negatively to the model output, while high reflectance values increase the predictions strongly toward Europe-E. This indicates that NIR reflectance is a strong spectral for identifying this class. MS-Red and MS-Green contribute significantly to the model's predictions, with MS-Red in particular showing a clear trend where high reflectance values are strongly associated with positive SHAP values. Finally, the SHAP plot for Europe-F reveals a relatively uniform and low-impact contribution across all spectral bands. MS-NIR and RGB-Red are the most influential bands in this class, though still modest in impact. For MS-NIR, high reflectance slightly boosts the prediction, while low reflectance values show negative SHAP values. A similar pattern is observed for RGB-Red, suggesting that Europe-F has an association with reflectance in the red and near-infrared spectrum.

V. DISCUSSION

Beyond the numerical classification performance of the ML and DL models cited in Table I, the results in fact demonstrate that these models align with the underlying geological and geophysical properties of bauxite. Specifically, as an ore, bauxite is composed of various minerals including a mixture of aluminum hydroxides (gibbsite, boehmite, and diaspore), iron oxides (goethite and hematite), kaolinite clay and titanium dioxide among others [34], [35], whose distribution depends on the region of origin and thus it is expected that each mineral will have different reflectance values across the measured spectrum [36]. According to [34], the lowest reflectance values from bauxite minerals occur in the 400–600 nm range, where two of the three bands from the RGB capture reflectance values, namely, RGB-Green and RGB-Blue, giving a potential justification to the reduced performance of the ML and DL models when only RGB data are used. On the contrary, given that the reflectance values of bauxite minerals are increased in the 600–1000 nm range [34], where MS-Red, MS-RedEdge, and MS-NIR from the MS capture spectral information, the ML and DL models performance is increased. Satisfactory classification performance is observed when all seven bands are included, attributed to the potential inclusion of bauxite characteristics existing within both the visible spectrum (RGB) like color and surface features and the nonvisible one (MS).

The SHAP analysis across all regional bauxite classes highlights key spectral dependencies offering valuable insights into the role of MS data in classification performance. In the European region, classes, such as Europe-A, Europe-B, and Europe-C, showed a strong relation with the information from the RGB sensor, particularly in the RGB-Red and RGB-Blue bands, which contributed positively to the classification. However, some classes like Europe-D, Europe-E, and Europe-F, SHAP results revealed to be more dependent on MS-NIR, suggesting that the visible spectrum alone is insufficient for accurate identification. This was also shown for Europe-E, where the classification was clearly driven by MS-NIR and MS-Red reflectance levels, aligning with domain knowledge of iron-rich or clay-heavy mineral signatures at those wavelengths [37]. Similar patterns were observed for South American bauxites. While South America-B relied mostly on the RGB-Green and RGB-Blue bands, classes such as South America-C and South America-D demonstrated different spectral dependencies where MS-NIR had an important influence on the prediction. In the African region, a more balanced spectral behavior was shown. SHAP analysis showed moderate influence across both RGB and MS bands, with MS-NIR, MS-Red, and MS-RedEdge moderately guiding the classification process.

The above qualitative results are quantitatively supported by the experimental results shown in Table IV, where individual and combined band exclusion was conducted to assess their impact on classification performance. The results demonstrate that the removal of specific MS bands leads to a significant drop in accuracy, precision, recall, and F1-score, confirming the importance of those features as revealed by the SHAP analysis. For instance, excluding MS-Green resulted in a drop in

TABLE IV
MLP CLASSIFICATION PERFORMANCE WITH EXCLUDED BANDS DRIVEN BY KERNEL SHAP

Excluded Bands	Accuracy (%)	Precision (%)	Recall (%)	F1-Score (%)
MS-RedEdge	88.15	88.29	88.15	88.14
MS-Red	89.02	89.04	89.02	89.01
MS-Green	90.48	90.51	90.48	90.47
MS-Green & MS-NIR	87.80	88.00	87.80	87.83
MS-Green & RGB-Green	88.72	88.79	88.72	88.71
None	91.13	91.19	91.13	91.13

First row: One excluded band. Second row: Two excluded bands. Third row: None excluded band.

F1-Score from 91.13% to 90.47%, confirming its considerable impact as identified in SHAP for classes like Europe-E and South America-D. More critically, removing both MS-Green and MS-NIR simultaneously caused performance to degrade further to 87.83%, highlighting the role these bands had in enhancing class separability, particularly for those with weak RGB contrast. Furthermore, by excluding only MS-RedEdge or MS-Red led to smaller drops, i.e., 88.14%–89.01%, suggesting these features are less influential overall, which aligns well with their consistently low SHAP values across most bauxite types. The final row of Table IV (“None”) shows that retaining all MS bands gives the highest performance across metrics, further validating the importance of full-spectrum data fusion.

VI. CONCLUSION

This work introduced BauXAItE, an XAI Framework for UAV multisensor-driven bauxite stockpile mapping and classification. It was demonstrated that using UAVs enables on-demand monitoring and mapping of targeted areas, while the RGB and MS sensors, along with their combination, allow obtaining spectral signatures information in a wide spectrum range. Experimental results using several ML and DL models demonstrated scaling performance determined by the sensor used; in the RGB case the RF algorithm resulted in the best values apart from precision in which the TabCNN was better, whereas for the MS case, the TabCNN resulted in the best performance with the RF follow. When using both spectrum ranges in a combined dataset, the MLP outclassed the TabCNN and the RF, surpassing 91% performance across all metrics. Considering the XAI results for each class, it was shown that Kernel SHAP highlights the hierarchy in the importance of the appearing bands, like MS-NIR, being critical for precisely mapping bauxite stockpiles. This proves to be a valuable tool in real-world mining operations as it guides the spectrum selection and paves the way toward spectrum-oriented data acquisition strategies that involve sensors with more granular capabilities like hyperspectral ones.

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